

Synthesis and characterization of an organotin-titanium sulfide polymer

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A polymer material has been synthesised by the reaction of dimethyltin sulphide and titanocene dichloride in methanolic medium. The product has been characterized as a sulfido bridged heterobimetallic coordination polymer of composition $[\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}]_n$ by elemental analyses, Mass, EDX, FTIR, solid state (^{13}C and ^{119}Sn) NMR, electronic absorption and emission spectroscopic methods. Powder X-ray diffraction and TGA studies revealed non-crystalline nature of the material. Theoretical calculations at DFT level have been performed on a truncated unit to simulate its spectral features. Variable temperature pressed pellet conductivity measurement revealed semiconducting nature with a narrow band gap of 0.79 eV of the material.

Keywords: Organotin, titanocene, polymeric material, metal sulfide, solid state Sn NMR.

Introduction

Tin sulphides are important materials in view of their technical applications. Both Sn^{II} and Sn^{IV} sulphides are semiconductors, however, the former has a narrow band gap while the latter one has a wide band gap¹. These sulphides have great potentials for photovoltaic applications due to their easy availability and non-toxic (compared to CdS, for instance) nature. It is well known that band gap of a semiconductor can be suitably tuned by introducing a dopant; if a transition metal is introduced the band gap of a semiconductor gets lowered. Over the past decade there is considerable interest in synthesizing molecular precursors which can be converted to chalcogenide materials via a low energy pathway². Our recent studies on a few heterobimetallic complexes have revealed how these can be converted to corresponding ternary oxides/sulfides^{3,4}. In view of these facts we have tempted to prepare hetero bimetallic precursors containing Sn^{IV} and Ti^{IV} . It is worth mentioning here that though Sn^{II} containing ternary sulfides of the composition SnTiS_3 and SnTi_2S_5 are well known⁵, however, to the best of our knowledge no bimetallic $\text{Sn}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}$ molecular precursor has yet been reported. During our studies we have recently attempted to prepare molecular sulfide, $\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\mu\text{-S})_2\text{SnMe}_2$ by the reaction of Cp_2TiSH_2 and Me_2SnCl_2 which yielded ionic complexes of composition $[\text{Cp}_6\text{Ti}_6\text{O}_8][\text{Bu}_3\text{Sn}_3\text{S}_3(\text{SH})_3\text{Cl}]_2$ and $[\text{Cp}_6\text{Ti}_6\text{O}_8]$

$[\text{n-Bu}_3\text{Sn}_3\text{S}_3(\text{SH})_3\text{Cl}]_2$ ^{6,7}. A search of literature revealed that there is a heterobimetallic sulfido complex, $(\text{Me}_3\text{SbS})_2\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_2$ ⁸ prepared using the organotin sulfide, $(\text{Me}_2\text{SnS})_3$. We attempted to exploit this organotin sulfide to make an organotin-titanium sulfido complex.

Experimental

Synthesis and subsequent handling of compounds were conducted under anhydrous condition. All solvents were of reagent grade quality and purified by standard methods carefully prior to their use⁹. Titanocene dichloride (Sigma Aldrich) was soxhlate extracted using toluene in which, it was partially soluble and recrystallized.

Solid state NMR data (^{13}C and ^{119}Sn) of compound were recorded on BRUKER DSX 300, NMR Spectrometer. Infra-red spectrum of the compound was recorded in the region $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a Varian 3100 FT-IR spectrophotometer as KBr discs. The DART-MS mass spectra was recorded on a JEOL-Accu TOF JMS-T100LC Mass Spectrometer having a DART (Direct Analysis in Real Time) source. Dry helium was used with 4 lpm flow rate for ionization at 350°C . Electronic absorption spectra of the compound in solid state was recorded using Shimadzu UV-1700 Pharmaspec spectrophotometer in the range 200 and 1100 nm. Emission spectrum of compound was recorded using Varian Cary Eclipse fluo-

rescence spectrophotometer. Pressed pellet electrical conductivity of the compound was recorded on the Kiethley-236 source measurement unit by employing a conventional two probe technique in the temperature range of 313–363 K

All theoretical calculations were performed with the GAUSSIAN 03W set of programs¹⁰. The effective core potential (ECP) standard basis set LANL2DZ¹¹ was utilized for all the atoms.

Synthesis of $(\text{Me}_2\text{SnS})_3$

This compound was prepared following the reported method¹². To the solution of Me_2SnCl_2 (3.0 g, 13.63 mmol) in THF (20 ml) was added the solution of triethyl amine (2.75 g, 27.22 mmol) in THF (10 ml). H_2S gas was passed with stirring for 2 h to the reaction mixture. A white precipitate was appeared which was filtered out and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure. Resulting solid was extracted with ether (25 mL) and the ethereal solution on standing gave a crop of crystals. Yield 75%.

Synthesis of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$

To the suspension of titanocene dichloride (0.700 g, 2.811 mmol) in 20 mL dry methanol was added $(\text{Me}_2\text{SnS})_3$ (0.508 g, 0.937 mmol) in 15 mL methanol. After stirring for a few minutes, the solution became clear which was then heated (with constant stirring) for 3 h. The colour of the reaction mixture changed from red to orange. The solution was kept under ambient conditions and the solvent was allowed to evaporate slowly. After a few days yellow-orange shiny plates appeared at the bottom of the vessel which were insoluble in all common solvents. Yield (based on Cp_2TiCl_2) 90%.

Results and discussion

The compound $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTi-Cl}$ was synthesized by the reaction of $(\text{Me}_2\text{SnS})_3$ with Cp_2TiCl_2 in 1:3 stoichiometric ratio. From the C, H, N elemental analytical data the empirical formula of the compound is proposed to be $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$. To confirm the presence of the metal ions Sn and Ti we have carried out EDX (Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy) analysis (Fig. 1) EDX analysis is applicable to atoms with $Z \geq 5$ and signals for H atom are not observable. The percentage of carbon in the observed spectrum was quite higher than the elemental analysis (and also from expected composition) because of the use of a carbon platform to keep the

Fig. 1. EDX spectrum of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$.

sample while recording the spectrum. As a result, the percentages of other elements obtained by EDX analysis are also not reliable. However, presence of the elements S, Cl, Sn and Ti could be confirmed by this analysis. The powdered compound was also studied by SEM (scanning electron microscopy) which revealed the presence of only one type of particles in the powder (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrograph of (200X) $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$.

Unfortunately, the compound once isolated from the solution (as solid) could not be re-dissolved in any common solvents (toluene, benzene, chloroform, ether, tetrahydrofuran, dimethylsulfoxide, dimethylformamide, acetonitrile, ethanol and water etc.). As a result, structural studies in solution using NMR could not be carried out. The DART mass spectrum of the compound did not show any molecular ion peak up to 1000 a.u., however, presence of several high intensity

peaks were observed in the mass spectrum between the M^+ range of 1000 to 1500 a.u. Peaks corresponding to certain molecular fragments could be identified and have been listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Mass fragmentation pattern for $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$

Sr. No.	Molecular fragments	Observed mass (a.u.)
1.	$\text{TiClSn}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S} [\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{TiClSSn}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}]_2\text{Ti}$	1032.02
2.	$\text{TiClSSn}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{TiClSSn}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}]_2\text{Ti}$	1064.99
3.	$[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{TiClSSn}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}]_3\text{Ti}$	1131.75
4.	$[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{TiClSSn}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}]_3\text{TiClC}_5\text{H}_5$	1231.04

Solid state NMR spectral analysis

For further characterization we have recorded ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the compound in solid state (Fig. 3). A broad peak was observed at 47.6 ppm due to the methyl carbons where as two signals at 120.9 and 133.0 were observed due to the Cp carbons. From analytical and mass spectral data it is evident that only one cyclopentadienyl group is present with each Ti^{IV} . The orange colour of the compound also suggests the presence of only one cyclopentadienyl groups per Ti in +4 oxidation state¹³. Possibly the two closely spaced cyclopentadienyl signals arose due to two different orientations of Ti-Cp units owing to packing in the solid state.

Fig. 3. ^{13}C Solid state NMR of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$.

As mentioned above once isolated from solution the compound becomes insoluble, attempts were made to crystallize the compound from the reaction mixture itself. On keeping for several days solvent of the reaction mixture slowly evaporated out leaving a crop of small pieces of yellow-orange solid.

Powder X-ray diffraction analysis

The solid piece of compound was subjected to X-ray diffraction (Fig. 4) which showed a broad peak at a 2θ value of 7.45. The nature of X-ray diffraction pattern suggested a non-crystalline (or poorly crystalline) nature of the solid which is a usually observed property of polymeric solids.

Fig. 4. Powder X-ray diffraction pattern for $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$.

Thermal analysis

The non-crystalline nature of the compound was also evinced by its thermal decomposition pattern. Thermogravimetric analysis of the compound has been carried out under dry dinitrogen atmosphere over a temperature range of +40 to +650°C (Fig. 5). The TGA plot did not show sharp decomposition at any particular temperature. Instead the compound slowly decomposed over a wide temperature range. The weight loss at 600°C (46%) is equivalent to the total hydrocarbon content, however, in absence of any additional support such as evolved gas analysis it will be too speculative to comment on the composition of the residue.

Fig. 5. TGA curve for $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$.

On the basis of the physico-chemical data the following polymeric structure of compound is tentatively proposed (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Proposed structure of a fragment of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$.

Structure simulation

The structure of a monomeric unit (truncated the S-M (M = Ti, Sn) bonds by replacing M by H atoms) was optimized using Allinger's MM2 force field¹⁴. The atomic coordinates obtained from the optimized structure were then used for further optimization by DFT method. The energy minimized structure of the monomeric unit is shown in Fig. 7. Some of the structural parameters are listed in Table 2.

Fig. 7. Simulated (DFT) structure of a monomeric unit of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$.

Electronic spectral features

The electronic absorption spectrum of the compound shows a sharp peak at 315 nm and two relatively broad peaks at 268, 375 and at 407 nm (Fig. 8). Usually the peaks at lower wavelengths are observed due to ligand to ligand and

Table 2. Geometrical parameters of $\text{CpTiClS}_2\text{Me}_2\text{Sn}$

Bond lengths (Å)	Bond angles (°)
Sn-S(1) = 2.53	Sn-S-Ti = 107.69
Sn-S(2) = 2.49	S-Ti-S = 100.59
Sn-C = 2.12	S-Sn-S = 104.68
Ti-S(1) = 2.27	C-Sn-S = 110.48
Ti-S(2) = 2.35	C-Ti-S = 86.07
Ti-C = 2.41	Cl-Ti-S = 103.57
Ti-Cl = 2.29	

Fig. 8. Absorption spectrum of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$.

ligand to metal charge transfers. Absorptions at higher wave lengths are on the other hand, due to metal to ligand charge transfers. To make an unequivocal assignment of the electronic transitions we have carried out some theoretical calculations. The results of time dependent density functional (TDDFT) calculations revealed that these absorptions are primarily due to ligand to metal charge transfers.

Transitions from sulfur $p\pi$ orbitals to the non-bonding titanium $d\pi$ orbitals are responsible for the absorptions at 270, 316, 378, 407, 433, 485 nm. The orbitals and absorption wavelengths have been depicted in Fig. 9.

The photoluminescent nature of the compound was exhibited when it was excited at 407 nm showing a sharp emission band at 442 nm (Fig. 10).

Conductivity measurements

Metal sulfides show interesting electrical properties. TiS_2 shows metallic conductivity at room temperature¹ while tin

Fig. 9. Selected orbital transition of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$. Digits printed on vertical lines are calculated wavelengths (nm) responsible for corresponding transitions.

Fig. 10. Emission spectrum of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$.

sulfides are semiconductors. The band gap varies from 0.85 eV in Sn_2S_3 to 1.3 eV in SnS and 2.17 in SnS_2 ^{15,16}. Doping in, TiS_2 is known to change its electrical properties drastically¹⁷. Though the structure of the compound $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$ is quite different from those of TiS_2 and the

sulfides of tin, however, it contains both the metals linked together by sulfide bridges. We thought it worthwhile to study its electrical conductivity in the solid state. Pressed pellet conductivity measurements at different temperatures showed semiconducting nature of the compound. Conductivity increased from 3.60×10^{-8} at 40°C to 4.20×10^{-6} S cm^{-2} at 90°C . A plot of log conductivity vs inverse of measurement temperature is given in Fig. 11. Band gap of the solid was found to be 0.79 eV from the slope of the line.

Fig. 11. Plot showing change in ($\log \sigma$) conductivity of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}$ as a function of (inverse of absolute) temperature.

Conclusions

A reaction of the cyclic $(\text{Me}_2\text{SnS})_3$ with Cp_2TiCl_2 yielded a polymeric compound $[\text{Me}_2\text{SnS}_2\text{CpTiCl}]_n$ which has been characterized by various physicochemical techniques and the structure of a monomeric unit optimized by quantum chemical calculations. Solid state conductivity measurements revealed the (narrow band gap) semiconducting nature of the polymeric material.

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